

Exploring sensory perception, appraisal and concern: An approach to support design activity

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Abstract

The fundamental first stage of product interaction is through sensory perception, which generates cognitive and affective experiences. Product perception through sensory feedback is a major component in the end user product appraisal that precedes the elicitation of product emotion. Sensory evaluation is connected to a set of concepts including *appraisal*, *concern* and goal oriented *objective*. The interplay between *stimulus* (in this case from sensory feedback) and *product concern*, which forms the basis for product appraisal, is key to understanding how design effort can affect the end user's product perception.

This research investigates the contribution that sensory information can make to the design process using a technique, *Experience Continuum Sampling* to explore the connection between sensory perception, appraisal and concern due to product interaction. This approach provides specific information related to product features experienced through sensory stimuli. The designer can weight sensory information and direct activity to optimise product design.

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Introduction

The basis of the first stage of product interaction is sensory. Perceiving the product through the senses is a fundamental mode of product encounter, which leads to cognitive and affective experiences. Research in product design and ergonomics has lately been focused in the fields of emotional response, and pleasurable experiences of product design (e.g., Porter, Chibber & Porter 2004, Norman 2004, Desmet 2002, Jordan 2000). These fields of research are informed by sensory information gained from product interaction. Understanding the sensory modes of interaction and how they relate to the design of products is therefore a precursor to designing affective and emotional aspects of products, and will contribute to usefully informing the design process. Overbeeke et al. (2002: 10) state that it is the designer's task to "*make the product's function accessible to the user whilst allowing for interaction with the product in a beautiful way. Aesthetics of interaction is his goal.*" They emphasise the importance of the designer focusing on designing the interaction and staying tuned to the experiential. Hara (2007: 156) further emphasises the importance of designs focus on sensory experience, "*An image generated in the human brain is a spectacle orchestrated through multiple sensory stimuli and revived memories. This is precisely where the designer works.*"

Accordingly, it is important to understand the senses as the starting point for the experiential interaction with products.

Berlyne (1971: 113) notes "*all stimuli that are registered by the nervous system have motivational effects, including the physiological indices of emotional impact*". According to Bonapace (2000) the world around is "*a supplier of stimuli that reach people through sensory channels which triggers the stimulus and response mechanisms*". These response mechanisms include: input – sensory stimuli from the environment; perception – what the individual receives after stimuli pass through psycho-sensorial filters; cognition – the consequent elaboration and decision-making; action – the result of the decision; output – the result of the action. Other authors have discussed the senses in relation to other parts of the product experience, especially parts related to feelings and emotions. The 'pleasurable products' (see, e.g., Jordan 2000) and 'emotional design' movements (see, e.g., Desmet 2002, Norman 2004) are based on the understanding of hedonic and emotional benefits arising from the aesthetic and sensory experience of products.

Emotions are frequently opposed to cognition (Visser, 2006, p. 6) and are sometimes considered to be based purely on sensory stimuli that do not contain any meaning, or to be the antithesis to reason (Damasio, 1996). While the emotional response as such is not the focus of this paper, the interrelatedness between affective and cognitive response is highly relevant. There is strong evidence that emotion and cognition are intimately related in that decision making is influenced by feelings and emotions (Tversky and Kahnemann, 1981; Bechara et al., 2000, p.295). Moreover, they are considered mutually dependent (see Norman, 2002, Ashby et al. 1999), in that emotion affects cognition (Carlson, 1997, p. 112) and cognition affects emotion, as shown by Ribert-Van De Weerd (in Visser, 2006, p. 6). Norman regards “both affect and cognition as information processing systems, where the cognitive system makes sense of the world and the affective system is judgmental” (Crilly et al., 2004, p.553). According to Visser (2006, p.7) emotion is involved in the control of activity and thus influences decision-making.

Desmet’s Basic Model of Emotion

Desmet (2002) regards emotion as the affective response evoked by the combination of product stimuli, subjective concerns and an appraisal. He states that emotions are a result of our assessment or appraisal of the product in light of our experience and concerns related to it. Desmet’s diagram of this model for assessing emotional response to product design is copied in Figure 1.

Figure1: Desmet’s basic model of emotion.

Perception of product interaction through sensory feedback is a major component in end user product appraisal that precedes the elicitation of product emotion. Previous experiences of assessing sensory-based perceptions of product design (Adank and Warell,

2006) indicate that evaluations exhibit a wide range of responses. Psychophysical research has shown that the same event viewed by different individuals can produce inherently variable perceptual responses (Mather 2006: 4). Dependence on sensory modalities governed by different individual perceptive characteristics makes every sensory experience a highly individual affair (Bonapace 2000). Connecting sensory responses and appraisals of products to user centred concerns will contextualise evaluations, making them more useful for design purposes.

Sensory Experience in Product Design and Development

Sensory assessment of product interaction provides experiences from immensely rich to impoverished. Sensory experience comes loaded with subjective assessments that lead to aesthetic interpretation, and the elicitation of emotions. A better understanding of the subjective sensory product experience informs understanding of the development of emotions, and enables design for affective sensory experience that leads to a pleasurable interaction with the product (e.g. Jordan 2000).

The process of perception involves responding to external stimuli from the sensory system: synthesizing, merging, combining and selectively accepting or rejecting sensory information along with other internal sources of information that comprise the variable factors and shifting aspects of the individual (Berlyne 1971: 96).

Stimuli are perceived through sensory receptors that contribute to pleasurable and meaningful product interaction. They are commonly classified as: vision, hearing, touch, balance, taste/smell (Mather 2006: 4). Although sensory receptors are mutable and can vary due to such factors as aging, disease, accidents, or abnormalities, briefly, the characteristics of these sensory receptors are:

- *Vision* - usually the first sense that engages when we experience a product. Vision both communicates the descriptive characteristics of a product and also allows us to assess the aesthetic qualities of what we see. Vision is the base for assumptions as to the other product qualities we are observing.
- *Hearing* - allows us to sense sound, unlike vision, in all directions and through opaque occluded objects (Mather 2006: 81). The tone, speed and pitch of what we

hear are all factors that are open to interpretations that can relate directly to the quality of product interaction.

- *Touch* - allows us to sense texture, temperature, pressure, pain and vibration. Touch requires tangible access to the product. Mather (2006) writes, “*Touch mediates our most intimate contact with the external world*”.
- *Balance* - lets us orientate ourselves and move through the external environment: walking, turning, running, upright and without falling, and while doing do, being able to maintain a focus on an independently moving object (Mather 2006: 64). Balance dictates how we physically manage the product with which we interact.
- *Taste and smell* - are generally not considered in the hard product sphere of industrial design. Smell is an immensely affective sense and fires strong associations with past experiences, memory, places, situations, and emotions. Taste is less sensitive than smell.

The affective qualities of these senses are such that consideration for their potential in product design should be made.

Characteristics of Sensory Experience

Sensory experiences that arise from person/product interactions display a range of characteristics. Desmet (2002: xii) identified these characteristics as: *Personal*: different people experience different emotions from the same product stimulus; *Temporal*: an individuals emotions towards a product will vary at different points of time; and *Mixed*: we can feel different emotions towards the same product simultaneously. We suggest the following characteristics to describe the nature of sensory experience: *Intimacy*, *Subjectiveness* and *Temporality*.

Intimacy

The intimacy of sensation is not only affected by the product type and the nature of the interaction but by the stimulus or set of stimuli that determine which senses, or sets of senses, are engaged. As a general rule, the more distant the experience of the product, the fewer the senses engaged. Often vision is the first sense that comes into play. As the

product experience moves closer in proximity, other sensory organs participate informing and building the intimacy of sensory experience through sensory immersion.

Subjectiveness

The subjectiveness of sensory perceptions gives rise to individually different experiences. The physiological functioning of the senses is essentially the same for all human beings although some individuals may have diminished or missing sensory functions: perception exhibits different characteristics dependent on e.g. age, sex, and culture (Mather 2006: 343) and is further mediated by factors including past experience and peer group. Where assessments of taste are at issue, the subjective perception of sensory information may be strong, as it is not mediated by an objective measure. Factors such as colour, proportions, and the overall product aesthetic, all contribute to the subjective experience.

Temporality

Sensory experience has a temporal quality that is influenced by the level of exposure to and familiarity with a product. Jordan (2000: 146) acknowledges the importance of considering the senses, perceptions and emotional experience of a product over time. Over time, our initial assessment of the product may be modified by subsequent interaction. We no longer notice the same stimuli as intently as we had in an earlier interactions, because we have grown used to various product characteristics such as aesthetic, feel, and operation. Imagine seeing a new scooter in a showroom – the first sensory contact is a distant visual experience, from which we base our decision to further engage in interaction with the product. If our visual judgment is favourable we may move to a closer proximity that affords further interaction involving other sensory stimuli: holding the handlebars, sitting on the seat, assessing comfort, feeling the textures, the tactility of throttle controls and indicator switches. After riding the scooter for a few months, the reaction to the scooter's visual aesthetic may be reduced and the experience of the comfort of the seat may become unconscious, while other aspects of the product come to the fore. The modality of the sensory experience, and the importance of certain senses, change to build a more complete 'picture' of the product and our experience of it.

Connecting the Senses to Design

Sensory evaluation is connected to a set of concepts including *appraisal*, *concern* and goal oriented *objective*. The interplay between *stimulus* (in this case from sensory

feedback) and product concern, which forms the basis for product appraisal, is key to understanding how design effort can affect product perception for the end user.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the contribution that sensory information can make to the design process. This paper explores the connection between multi-modal sensory perception and the manifestation of the designed product, in order to contribute to an approach whereby sensory perception is used as a starting point to support design activity. The paper connects the evolving framework to *Five Senses Testing: Experience Continuum Sampling* (Adank & Warell 2006, Adank & Warell inpress) and develops this technique further.

Enlightening Concern

This paper describes the technique of *Experience Continuum Sampling* that has been designed to elucidate, through product interaction, the *end user concern* described in Desmet's basic model of emotion (see Figure 1). Concerns are seen as drivers for product design and development. Concerns identified throughout a range of stages during product interaction, can form the basis for product innovation. *Experience Continuum Sampling* assesses user experience of product interaction with respect to multi-sensory stimuli related to active features of the product. *Reflective comments* provided by users describe the issues they perceive. The investigator translates these perceived issues as *hidden concerns*, which can then be transformed into design criteria and used to drive design processes. The resulting improved products will alleviate perceived issues and meet concerns. The reflective comments and sensory assessments of the product's active feature may also be developed to assist in identifying the latent needs of the end user.

Experience Continuum Sampling

Experience Continuum Sampling (Adank & Warell 2006, Adank & Warell inpress) provides, through sensory experience, in-depth, specific information related to product features and experiences. It attempts to consider the *intimacy*, *subjectiveness* and *temporality* of sensation by sampling specific stages along a continuum of person/product interaction. The person/product experience continuum refers to the continuum of product experience from the first to the last interaction with the product. It usually describes a number of distinct stages specific to the product type (Figure 2.) and the nature of the interaction the product requires in use.

Figure 2: A sample of stages from the person/product experience continuum for a 2-stroke garden trimmer.

Experience Continuum Sampling involves the following procedures:

- A range of product interactions along the person/product experience continuum is identified, and from this range, a stage that represents a specific activity of interaction is selected for sampling.
- The investigator prepares a feedback form (see Figure 3 for an example of the form). The form includes: the stage on the experience continuum being sampled; a description of the trial and the respondent; a visual analogue scale to accommodate ratings for each of the five senses; a place holder for the active product feature that will be identified by the sampling; and space for reflective comments. Images of the product and the respondent in context are also desirable for the reference information they provide.
- Suitable respondents are selected from the target market for the product and the stage of interest is explained to the respondent.
- The field trial, which involves the respondent, in the presence of the investigator, interacting with the product, is conducted.
- After the trial, the investigator interviews the respondent to assess the quality of the sensory experience for each of the five senses; identifies the active feature of the product that provides that experience; and elicits a reflective comment on the relationship between sensory information and the active feature.
- The investigator reviews and analyses the results to identify areas of further design activity. Subjective information from the reflective comment and the sensory assessment is linked directly to the active feature of the product. The performance of the active feature can now be judged in terms of the sensation it provides.

The five main benefits offered by Experience Continuum Sampling are:

- Sensory modes are linked to the product feature.
- It separates sensory information and makes it apparent what modes are in use.
- It takes the investigator into the environment of the respondent, providing high quality of information and a measure of objectivity.
- The technique forces consideration of all the senses.
- Clear sensory information can be obtained in relation to a specific stage of interaction.

Three significant limitations of the technique are:

- The technique works best with an existing product or well-developed product concept.
- Where the investigators are considering an existing product, the technique may tend to support incremental improvements rather than radical innovations.
- The technique needs to be well thought out and requires forward planning.

Stage 1: Preparation

Stage 2: Refuelling

Stage 3: Loading line

Stage 4: Starting

Stage 5: Trimming

Stage 6: Adjusting

Stage 7: Storage

Five Senses Testing : Experience Continuum Sampling

Stage No. 5 of 7

Trial Description: Trimming

Domestic use, 35 yr male, trimming a rough steep section.

	Negative	0	Positive	
Vision			X	Active Feature Strim Head
Sound		X		Exhaust
Touch		X		Handles/shaft
Balance		X		Motor
Smell/Taste		X		2-stroke/exhaust

Product & Context (visual reference)

Reflective Comment:

It's easier to use with a smaller trim guard, the last one I had was too big and made it hard to see what was going on.

It's not too noisy, especially if you have muffs but annoys those nearby a bit.

Generally not too bad, however a bit of a balancing act down a bank. You end up supporting it with your forearm sometimes.

The taste doesn't worry me its just the petrol and exhaust smell stays with you.

Figure 3: Feedback form from an investigation into a 2-stroke garden line trimmer.

From Appraisal and Stimulus back to Concern

By aligning the outcomes from the Experience Continuum Sampling with sectors of Desmet's 'Model of basic emotion' we can then extrapolate back to identify the 'hidden concern' (see Figure 4) that along with the 'stimulus' underpins the product experience

‘appraisal’. The reflective comment; the sensory assessment (using the visual analogue scale); and the person/product continuum (specific stage), informs the appraisal stage. The active feature of the product provides the stimulus for the sensory mode (vision, hearing, touch, balance, taste/smell) engaged. This further informs the appraisal.

Figure 4: Identifying the hidden concern

Analysis of the information provided in the feedback form helps sheds light on the hidden concern that the end user may have at this particular point along the person/product experience continuum. This is extremely useful: it is this elusive hidden concern that is needed to push the design response. Through design iteration the ‘hidden concerns’ can be integrated into the development process through their influence on design activity. This enhances the probability of affecting the quality of the subsequent appraisal and the elicitation of a positive emotional experience: as Desmet (2002 p108) states *“a product only elicits an emotion if it is appraised as relevant to a persons concern.”*

Case Study Example Results

Using the sample feedback sheet in Figure 3, we can develop a range of ‘hidden concerns’ for the 2-stroke garden line trimmer-for this particular sample stage no.5 of 7: Trimming. The concerns extracted through sensory assessment directly drive design criteria and responses (see Figure 5).

Product: 2-Stroke Garden Line Trimmer Stage: 5 of 7 - Trimming (rough steep terrain).			
	Vision: was rated moderately positive.	Sound: was rated slightly negative.	Touch: was rated moderately negative.
	Stimulus - Trimming head (active product feature).	Stimulus - Exhaust (active product feature).	Stimulus - Motor (active product feature).
	Reflective Comment: It's easier to use with a smaller trim guard, the last one I had was too big and made it hard to see what was going on.	Reflective Comment: It's not too noisy, especially if you have muffs but annoys those nearby a bit.	Reflective Comment: Generally not too bad, however a bit of a balancing act down a bank. You end up supporting it with your forearm sometimes.
	Hidden Concern: - Being able to easily see what the trimming line is cutting. - Being sure you are not cutting too close to plants you wish to keep.	Hidden Concern: - The noise is annoying for others in the vicinity. - Have I got my earmuffs? - It is damaging to my hearing.	Hidden Concern: - Maintaining balance while operating product on sloping ground. - Being able to easily present the trimming head for steep banks.
	Design Criteria: User must have clear view of trimming line during operation.	Design Criteria: - Decibel rating of 60 -70 dB (normal conversation). - Exhaust should have a satisfying sound.	Design Criteria: - Product should not destabilize user's balance. - User needs control of position of trimming head.
	Design Response: - Optimise trimming head guard for visibility. - Relocate guard location to further up the main shaft. - Mark perimeter of whirling trimming line to aid accuracy - laser ?	Design Response: - Noise should be suppressed to a level where earmuffs are not required. - Earmuffs to clip onto the product as an integrated component. - Design the exhaust sound.	Design Response: - Improve fuel filling process to eliminate spillage, overflowing, contact with fuel. - Design muffler to eliminate smells as well as noise.

- Stage 1: Preparation
- Stage 2: Refuelling
- Stage 3: Loading line
- Stage 4: Starting
- Stage 5: Trimming**
- Stage 6: Adjusting
- Stage 7: Storage

Figure 5: Example analysis matrix from Experience Continuum Sampling feedback sheet for a garden trimmer.

Five points arising from this analysis results matrix illustrate possible areas for investigation and development:

- Having a neutral sensory result and no Reflective Comment recorded can stimulate design criteria and response in order to affect a positive change through the very intimate sense of touch.
- That sound (an often overlooked experience in product design) has a clear and direct impact on the consequent design direction with three design alternatives for dealing with noise and its consequence identified.
- Balance is identified as a problem as a consequence of steep terrain and results in an unforeseen handling/utility situation (supporting the motor in a raised position on the forearm in order to present the trimming head at the right angle for the steep terrain).
- The reflective comment for Smell/Taste identified a problem that was probably a failure of the filling process in an earlier stage (This result should be compared to the results from Stage 2: Refuelling).
- Although Vision rated well the Reflective Comment identified aspects of the guard design that could be developed to improve the end user experience of quality and product satisfaction.

Conclusions

Sensory feedback is measurable. When it is assessed as being linked to product attributes, it may be used to identify and analyse the *product concern*, usefully informing the design process. *Experience Continuum Sampling* provides specific information related to product features experienced through sensory stimuli.

Experience Continuum Sampling can be applied at any point along the product experience continuum. By looking at more sample points during the continuum of the use process, we gain more information. The continuum sampling decision is important in shaping the sensory information reported and the extraction of end user product concerns.

Sampling a specific interaction along the product-person continuum narrows the scope of the end user product concerns and the range of information being reported from sensory stimuli. The sensory information produced, which is linked to product features, can aid in

identifying the concern that underpinned the appraisal. This information can be weighted to express the perceived value it may have within a product development process.

The information gained through this approach is useful because by understanding the product concern in relation to the product stimulus, derived from sensory input (and linked to product attribute), we can more readily direct design activity in subsequent product iterations to optimise the stimulus for the identified product concerns.

Investigators can better predict and understand the appraisal made during product interaction. Using this approach should yield information that helps keep designers attuned to the sensory experience of the end user and enables them to produce a product that elicits the desired emotion.

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